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Big data for buildings

Building Information aGGregation, harmonization and analytics platform

Project N° 957047

D8.1 - Marketing material and website

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Executive Summary

The BIGG project aims at demonstrating the application of big data technologies and data analytic techniques for the complete buildings life-cycle of more than 4000 buildings in 6 large-scale pilot test beds, achieved by: 1) The Open Source BIGG Data Reference Architecture 4 Buildings for collection/funneling, processing and exchanging data from different sources (smart meters, sensors, BMS, existing data sets); 2) An interoperable buildings data specification, BIGG Standard Data Model 4 Buildings, based on the combination of elements from existing frameworks and EC directives, such as SAREF, INSPIRE, BIM, EPCHub that will be enhanced to reach full interoperability of building data; 3) An extensible, open, cloud-based BIGG Data Analytics Toolbox of service modules for batch and real-time analytics that supports a wide range of services, new business models and support reliable and effective policy-Making. These solutions will be deployed and tested cross pilot and country validation of at least two business scenarios in Spain and Greece.

This deliverable describes the first set of marketing materials that will be used for the BIGG project communication, aiming at guaranteeing broad visibility and promotion to the project's activities. It includes the description of the project visual identity, the project website, the social media profiles that have been created and the format of basic communication elements (poster, flyers, ppt presentations).

This is the first deliverable of Work Package 8, and it will be complemented by *D8.2 - Dissemination and communication actions plans and target KPIs*, that will identify how to use this material during the project.

This material will be updated as well as more elements will be added in the set as required by the project.

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Table of Acronyms and Definitions

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
D	Deliverable
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
SN	Social network
WP	Work package

I. INTRODUCTION

I.1. Purpose and organization of the document

This deliverable D8.1 shows the marketing materials and the website created for BIGG project. It covers a comprehensive overview on the development of the project design including the logo, the first draft of communication channels and related content.

After this introduction, Section II describes the elements that compose the project visual identity, Section III explains the project website and Section IV refers to the material related to the social network. Section V explains the main document conclusions and the future actions to be taken with respect to this material during the project execution.

I.2. Scope and audience

Five main communication and dissemination objectives have been identified at the beginning of the project:

1. Coordination of project dissemination and communication activities;
2. Attractive and up-to-date project presentation (online and beyond);
3. Presence of the project collaboration and results at selected liaison events;
4. Publications in research journals and proceedings (peer reviewed);
5. To spread BIGG concept, activities and results in the regions/countries of the BIGG practice partner and beyond.

To this end, all communication and dissemination activities of BIGG will be supported by high-quality marketing material. The first set has been developed within WP8 (*Task 8.1 – Communication strategy and material*) from months one to three of the project. The aim was the creation of an appealing brand identity. Based on this corporate identity, a website was set up displaying information about the project, its partners and with sections for news, events and media. For a consistent dissemination of BIGG concepts and results, templates for PowerPoint and deliverables were also created following brand and corporate identity.

These elements are helping to define the main marketing and communication guidelines that will be developed in the 2nd deliverable of this work package (D8.2 - *Dissemination and communication actions plans and target KPIs*) and during the whole duration of the project.

From the BIGG Consortium, ECTP is the leader of WP8 – Public Outreach and of its task *Liaisons, stakeholders' engagement and other synergies*, Inetum BE is the leader of the first task *Communication strategy and material* while IMEC leads the second task *Dissemination plan and activities*. The three partners worked together in the production of this first round of elements. Under this collaboration framework, it was agreed that ECTP will organize and manage all the social media aspects and website content, while Inetum BE will be focused on the website and other marketing materials design.

The document is addressed to all public, including non-expert readers.

All marketing materials will be developed firstly in English and then translated into different EU languages when targeting specific national-ambit audiences within a particular country.

The Consortium partners are aware of the current limitations due to the Covid-19 pandemic, which will have effects on the communication strategy, especially when it comes to participation to in-site events and conferences. This impact will be analysed as part of the D8.2. The partners leading communication activities worked firstly to deliver the elements that characterize the online communication (starting from website and social media).

II. VISUAL IDENTITY

An essential aspect to enhance BIGG project's visibility and identity is image branding. Visual identity in BIGG includes the generation of the project logo, colours and fonts; as well as corporate design guidelines and templates. All these elements will be applied on project materials as well as on all internal documents of the consortium members and stakeholders to create a cohesive representation of the project.

II.1. Logo design and concept

The process that led to the definition and subsequent adoption of the logo, representing the idea behind the BIGG project, required the active involvement of all partners.

As first action, the visual designer assigned to the project by Inetum BE (responsible for this task) studied the project context, analysing which elements should be represented in the project visual material. As result, four different logos were designed as shown in the next figures:

Figure 1 - First logo proposal and its concept

Figure 2 - Second logo proposal and its concept

Figure 3 - Third logo proposal and its concept

Figure 4 - Forth logo proposal and its concept

Then, the proposals were exposed to the partners in an online meeting. After explaining the logic behind each idea, the proposals were shared in an online poll in which all participants had the opportunity to express their preferences.

Figure 5 - Voting options

The competition resulted in the selection of the first logo. Colors were then added to it, resulting on the final version of the logo shown below:

Figure 6 – BIGG final logo

The colour palette to be used in the project marketing material is therefore defined by the logo:

Colors

Figure 7 - BIGG main colour palette

Considering dissemination goals, the logo will be included in all types of marketing material (e.g., project folders, presentations, videos) and will be used for all templates and publications (e.g., deliverables).

Both the symbol and the name can be used considering the different location, dimension and position they could have in the different documents (online or on paper) as different formats are available.

Figure 8 - Logo in different formats

II.2. Fonts

Default fonts are also shared in order for all material to follow the one of the logo:

Font

Print and website

Acumin Light for titles

Acumin Black for highlights or subtitles

Acumin Medium for default text

Acumin Medium Italic for quotes or highlights

MS Office and default

Arial Regular for titles

Acumin Bold for highlights or subtitles

Acumin Regular for default text

Acumin Italic for quotes or highlights

II.3. Power Point template

Using the BIGG logo and colour palette and following the H2020 guidelines, the template for the PowerPoint presentation that will be used by all partners throughout the project was designed by Inetum BE. Some of its slides are shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9 - Presentation template

II.4. Deliverable templates

Deliverable templates have been created and provided to all the consortium partners, a Word document as the one used for this deliverable D8.1.

Figure 10 - Deliverable template

II.5. Posters and flyers template

Posters and flyers templates have been introduced starting from the same basic elements previously cited (BIGG logo and colour palette, H2020 guidelines).

There are two main typologies of templates: online templates and printed templates. Both typologies will follow general guidelines. Online will use RGB color, print will use CMYK color and in terms of output file types, the online versions will be presented as an interactive pdf.

Posters are designed basing on same proportion formats (A4 and A1); flyers are designed from A4 format divided in 3 sections.

Figure 11 - BIGG example of a poster

Figure 12 – BIGG example of a flyer

III. BIGG PROJECT WEBSITE

The BIGG website will be the main communication tool of the project, constituting an international showcase for all interested parts. BIGG website will facilitate a prompt and continuous flow and exchange of information between the partners and the project stakeholders thus, promoting social awareness and stakeholder engagement.

Partners will refer to BIGG's website in their own websites to increase the visibility of the project. They will also promote project actions and messages through their own social media channels.

The BIGG project website has been designed, developed by Inetum BE and operated by ECTP, Inetum BE and IMEC. The website serves as the major dissemination and information channel of the project. It includes dynamic elements, being main website functionalities:

- The web design is responsive and includes all elements for search engine optimization (SEO) as well as social media sharing.
- It includes all the relevant information about the project, its goals and objectives, the consortium partners and its WPs.
- Provide regular news and information regarding BIGG activities and results.
- Include links to Social Media to be attractive to the public.
- It will disseminate the different solutions and co-created materials generated by the consortium
- It will disseminate the repository providing Open Access to scientific publications and research data collected within the project implementation

KPIs for BIGG website are defined in deliverable D8.2.

The URL of the website is: <https://www.bigg-project.eu> (bigg-project.eu can be used). The objective of the design is to be modern and attractive to navigate through, including attractive images and pictures. Project explanatory text is concise, giving the reader the key messages to well understand the project while not being heavy. In addition, as the website can be consulted by all types of building sector actors, the content is not technically-oriented. The visitor will find the essential messages related to his/her area of expertise, inviting then to register to the project newsletter or to get contact to the project partners for further specific area information.

The elements that compose the website are the following:

The home page: It's a summary of the main elements of the website, and an invitation for further navigating the website, with a project intro, an intro for the Objectives & Expected Impact, an overview of the project publications and the partners icons and links to their corresponding websites. It is expected that before the first press release and newsletter is released, the website includes a form for visitors to subscribe to the project newsletters.

Figure 13 - BIGG project website home page

The Project, which is divided in “Our scope”, “Our challenges” and “Our real-case demonstrations”.

Figure 14 - "Our Scope" page

In “Our challenges” the visitor can find information about the project objectives and the expected impacts.

Figure 15 – Project objectives in “Our Challenges” page

CASE STUDY AREA: SPAIN

Catalunya

MAIN TARGETS

Needs of the public administrations to enhance the data gathering and analysis for monitoring the performance and improving the energy efficiency of the building stock.

- Gather and harmonize data stored in different databases (regional, research databases, cadastre (land registry), meteorological data, building certification data, monitoring data, modelling data)
- Data driven support to energy policy design and implementation: Current state evaluation (Baseline), General Fault detection, Policy decision support and Evaluation of policies applied
- Improvement of Energy Performance Certification, Comparability with EPC of other Spanish regions and EU countries
- Building renovation decision support: Selection of the most appropriate EEM to apply and De-risking of energy efficiency investments

BUSINESS CASES

1. Benchmarking and energy efficiency tracking in public buildings
2. Energy certification in residential and tertiary buildings
3. Building life-cycle – From planning to renovation

CASE STUDY AREA: GREECE

Athens

MAIN TARGETS

17 large commercial office buildings in Athens managed through Energy Performance Contracting (EPC) or Maintenance Contract. The pilot site will demonstrate the application of EPC-based management for commercial buildings. Focus will be on continuously optimizing the building operation-consumption, to guarantee comfort of occupants, by controlling HVAC systems/lighting.

- Energy Performance Contract-based savings in commercial buildings
- Buildings for occupants: Comfort case

BUSINESS CASES

1. Energy Performance Contract-based savings in commercial buildings
2. Buildings for occupants: Comfort case

CASE STUDY AREA: GREECE

Volos & Thessaloniki

MAIN TARGETS

Residential consumers can tune the operation of their heating system through a smartphone application and let the controller optimally adapt the heating operation to their comfort limits, weather conditions and building characteristics.

The pilot site will demonstrate the application of Demand Response management on top of electricity and gas consumers

BUSINESS CASES

1. Electricity and Gas demand-response

Figure 18 – “Our Demonstrations” page

In Publications, for the moment it only includes the news about the project launch. In the future, it will include the press releases, the blog posts – linked to the social networks content, scientific and white papers both produced by the project and those from external entities related to the project context and the public deliverables of the project.

Figure 19 – “Publications” page

IV. PROJECT SOCIAL MEDIA PROFILES

Dissemination of the BIGG activities and results is also carried out using social media, targeting both professional and public networks.

Social Media channels will be created to promote participation of stakeholders and to strengthen the visibility and impact of the project results. Holding an active social media presence will attract the interest of stakeholders and the general public and will serve to make the virtual community grow.

Social Media channels will be fed with news, updated content from the website and other contents published by the stakeholders involved in the sector and related to BIGG. This will allow to create an active and participatory community of followers around the project, and to increase the visits to the BIGG website.

Partners should consider the following aspects in order to hold an active and relevant presence in social media and to provide information of interest to the public and stakeholders:

- Use the hashtags of the project: #BIGG, #H2020
- Take advantage of any audiovisual material to be disseminated in social media channels.
- Report communicative milestones to ECTP and Inetum BE in order to be supported.
- Participate in the conversation on social media channels.
- Monitor basic data from their own Social Media profiles/accounts

Guidelines for the use of social media channels developed for partners, including good practices for interacting with social media accounts will be included in the communication and dissemination plan within D8.2.

For the moment, two social media profiles are active for BIGG in order to foster networking:

- A group in LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/9021252/>
- A Twitter account: <https://twitter.com/BiggProject>

At the beginning, LinkedIn will be the most active social network in order to create synergies and awareness among related professional communities. Connections to other projects, stakeholders, associations and interested organizations will firstly occur via LinkedIn. Once the project is generating content, Twitter will be constantly fed to reach other type of audience: General public interested in urban sustainability, to which buildings are an essential contributor.

In the future, the project might consider Facebook if specific campaigns occur, e.g., empowerment/engagement of specific groups in the trials (residents, office occupants, local businesses, etc).

As the world of social media is changing very fast, adaptations of the profiles during the 36 months of the project are likely to occur. One case to be analysed, later in the project, is Instagram. This SN account, mostly for sharing stories, has the power to be connected and fed by both partners' corporate accounts and personal ones; therefore, experiences during the trials could be shared by the project partners as well as by trials participants.

Social media channels will facilitate establishing meaningful connections with an active and relevant international network of current and potential stakeholders. These connections will produce beneficial opportunities for BIGG network of stakeholders beyond communication and dissemination purposes.

KPIs for Social Media channels are: impressions, clicks, likes, shares, comments, mentions, followers, views...

Main actions to be carried out:

- Create a network of followers/fans/subscribers
- Keep in touch with partners and stakeholders
- Announce events, conferences, meetings, workshops and relevant milestones
- Use hashtags to disseminate events, conferences, workshops, etc.
- Live transmission of events, conferences, workshops, etc.
- Disseminate promotional video/animations of the project
- Disseminate promotional videos of events, conferences, workshops, etc.
- Connect with related initiatives at national and European level
- Search trends and tendencies related to the project (news, videos, projects, resources, etc.)

The marketing strategy suggests having a common graphical visualization (considering the specificity of each single social network) and to use the above-mentioned thematic icons for each communication that could refer to them.

The specific characteristics of the selected social media and their particular preferences of the heterogeneous public that will use of them, implies possible differences in the management of the profiles. Nevertheless, the graphical identity is mainly extracted from the website. Colours, logos and images will be repeated in every online platform in order to match as much as possible with the brand identity.

Figure 20 - LinkedIn profile

Figure 21 - Twitter profile

Figure 22 - LinkedIn header

Figure 23 - Twitter header

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE ACTIONS

The report details the guidelines to produce marketing material in the project. It sets up the basic elements (templates, colours, fontst) that will be further developed in the future according to the project needs.

In the core of this marketing material, the project website has been released.

Future actions, within the framework of Communication actions, are planned and listed below:

- The BIGG project website will be updated regularly including technical articles, reviews, press releases and project public deliverables as well as new dissemination material;
- The project brochure, poster and factsheet templates will be adapted to support web visualization and then in print version;
- Project newsletters will be published and distributed as long as the project starts to propose novelties;
- The project social media profiles will be updated several times a month. Interesting news related to the project or EU initiatives will be posted and disseminated to the project's followers;
- Any other activity, like an article or paper etc. will be prepared and publicized according to the project's needs.

The future activities will be strictly oriented to reach the KPI goals as they have been defined in the Description of the Action of the Grant Agreement and reviewed in D8.2 - Dissemination and Communication Action Plans and Target KPIs.

